

An optimized tactile sensing technology built for an anthropomorphic robotic hand

1st Avinash Kumar Singh

ITEE

Universit'a degli Studi di Napoli Federico II
Napoli, Italy

avinashkumar.singh@unina.it

2nd Petros Kaltsas

Mechanical Engineering

University of Patras
Athens, Greece

petrosikaltsas@gmail.com

3rd Fanny Ficuciello

ITEE

Universit'a degli Studi di Napoli Federico II
Napoli, Italy

fanny.ficuciello@unina.it

Abstract—The Prisma Hand II is an anthropomorphic multi functional robotic hand developed at PRISMA Lab, University of Naples Federico II which provides a solution for in-hand manipulation during grasping tasks. Each fingertip integrates a tactile/force sensor based on optoelectronic technology, providing tactile/force feedback during grasping and manipulation, particularly useful with deformable objects. The abstract proposes a new solution for the design and calibration of optimized sensors taking reference from the old sensors built based on the same technology.

Index Terms—Under actuation; Tactile sensing; Neural Networks Architectures; In-hand Manipulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Current medical industries face a remarkable challenge or replacement of a missing limb through trauma, disease, or any congenital disorder present from birth in upper limb amputees known as Prosthesis. Taking into consideration the needs of the patient, several factors like weight, design, usage complexities, and grasping capabilities of the robotic hand should serve the purpose. Taking into consideration the target applications, there always exists a trade-off between the factors. For industrial purposes, one can use a fully actuated mechanism to obtain precision but lacks versatility. On the other hand for prosthesis-related applications, under-actuated hands can be beneficial for daily activities as they are lightweight because of the presence of fewer motors and compliant. Some previous examples include Bebionic Hand (Ottobock GmbH.) [1] and the i-Limb Hand (Touch Bionics Ltd.) [2]. Prisma Hand II consists of Compliant Rolling-contact Elements (CORE) joint as referenced in the case of PISA/IIT SoftHand [3] and the soft HAND Pro-H [4]. The tactile sensing technology mentioned in the paper was implemented to improve the manipulation of the hand during grasping. The sensor presented in this paper uses the same taxel-based sensing technology based on optoelectronic tactile sensors [5].

II. DESIGN AND SENSING SYSTEM OF PRISMA HAND II

A. Mechanical design

The PRISMA hand II has 19 joints and three motors, while each finger incorporates three flexion/extension joints consisting of compliant rolling joints. The thumb has one rotation

joint, while the other fingers have one abduction/adduction joint. [6] The current supported framework of the hand includes PC or Raspberry Pi 3B [7].

Fig. 1. Prisma Hand II Structure

B. Fingertip Tactile Sensing Technology and Calibration

The construction of the sensing technology includes the use of a PCB acquainted with LED-photo transistor couples further covered by a deformable elastic layer positioned above the photo couples. The optimized sensors consist of a matrix structure of photo transistor couples (3X3) allowing us to utilize a combination of force and torque values from an ATI sensor as an input for training a neural network. The relationship established between voltage and force (X, Y, Z) is done using a 3 axis ATI F/T sensor as a force/torque reference during the calibration process. The calibration process is carried out by recording 140000 samples of voltage and relative forces at a frequency of 100 Hz using ROS. 2 kinds of neural networks mainly Artificial neural networks(ANN) and Convolutional Neural networks(CNN) are trained on the data samples and comparisons are made on the performance of the neural network models based on their force predictions after training. The parameter for the selection of the best model is based on the lowest MSE value in the prediction phase of experiments and elaborates its use in real-time grasping situations. The parameters for training the Artificial neural network consist of loss and metrics being the Mean squared

error (MSE) with optimizer as Adam, batch size of 64 and 300 epochs. The CNN comprises 2 convolutional layers of 256 and 64 neurons in addition to a dense layer of 16 neurons. Later, increment of layers in the same model of CNN was made to improve the learning ability of the network. In this architecture, 5 convolutional layers are chosen with 128,64,32,32 and 16 neurons respectively. The samples are split into 80 percent of training data and 20 percent of validation data. The output is expected to be 3 axis of forces(X, Y, Z).

Fig. 2. Setup for Calibration of Sensor

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To compare the performance of precision for the prediction capabilities between ANN and CNN trained, an experiment is conducted in 2 phases mainly being push and sliding conditions on the fingertip pad. Theoretically, during the push experiment the network should precisely predict the Z axis forces concerning the ATI reference sensor whereas, during the sliding experiment, the network should predict precise X and Y-axis forces. After comparison of MSE values we conclude that CNN performs better than ANN due to low MSE values in the prediction phase. MSE values upon observation clearly depict that the network loses the accuracy of force prediction when torque values are included in a CNN architecture. The MSE values upon observation also depict that the CNN performance in case of increment of layers is more accurate in force prediction with respect to fewer layers. Therefore, the best solution taking into consideration both slip and push conditions is the application of Convolutional Neural Networks. The increment of layers in the CNN is considered to be the best model for the inference of Force and torque values with respect to ATI reference sensor values as shown in (Fig. 3) and (Fig. 4). On the contrary, to predict only the force values, especially during the push conditions, a CNN with torque inclusion loses the accuracy in prediction as compared to a CNN trained with only force values as shown in (Fig. 5).

Fig. 3. Comparative prediction of Z axis force using CNN with less layers(CNN1) and more layers (CNN2) during push experiment

Fig. 4. Comparative prediction of X and Y axis force using CNN with less layers(CNN1) and more layers (CNN2) during slide experiment

Fig. 5. Comparative prediction graph of Z axis force using CNN with torque (CNNt) and without torque (CNN) during push experiment

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

To conclude, the paper includes construction of an optimized sensor based on optoelectronic technology present on an anthropomorphic robotic hand named Prisma Hand II. The application of neural networks on the sensors is presented and a further detailed comparison of various neural network techniques is done to select the best performing network. Future work focuses on the elaboration of force control for the improvement of in-hand manipulation of objects.

V. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research leading to these results has been supported by the PRINBOT project, in the frame of the PRIN 2017 research program, grant number 20172HHNK5_002.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. T. Belter, J. L. Segil, and B. SM, "Mechanical design and performance specifications of anthropomorphic prosthetic hands: a review," *Journal of rehabilitation research and development*, vol. 50, no. 5, p. 599, 2013.
- [2] O. Van Der Niet and C. K. van der Sluis, "Functionality of i-limb and i-limb pulse hands: Case report," *Journal of rehabilitation research and development*, vol. 50, no. 8, p. 1123, 2013.
- [3] M. G. Catalano, G. Grioli, E. Farnioli, A. Serio, C. Piazza, and A. Bicchi, "Adaptive synergies for the design and control of the pisa/iit soft-hand," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 768–782, 2014.
- [4] C. Piazza, M. G. Catalano, S. B. Godfrey, M. Rossi, G. Grioli, M. Bianchi, K. Zhao, and A. Bicchi, "The soft-hand pro-h: a hybrid body-controlled, electrically powered hand prosthesis for daily living and working," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 87–101, 2017.
- [5] A. Cirillo, P. Cirillo, G. D. Maria, C. Natale, and S. Pirozzi, "Force/tactile sensors based on optoelectronic technology for manipulation and physical human–robot interaction," in *Advanced Mechatronics and MEMS Devices II*. Springer, 2017, pp. 95–131.
- [6] H. Liu, P. Ferrentino, S. Pirozzi, B. Siciliano, and F. Ficuciello, "The prisma hand ii: a sensorized robust hand for adaptive grasp and in-hand manipulation," in *The International Symposium of Robotics Research*. Springer, 2019, pp. 971–986.
- [7] J. Newmarch, "Introduction to the raspberry pi," in *Raspberry Pi GPU Audio Video Programming*. Springer, 2017, pp. 1–5.